

UDC: 351

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10635270

THE WORLD EXPERIENCE OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION OF MONOPOLY ACTIVITY

Valentina Kupriyanova

PhD in Economics, Associate Professor,
Professor of the Department of Economics and Public Administration,
National Aerospace University “Kharkiv Aviation Institute”
ORCID ID: 0009-0003-6330-1935

Abstract. The article is aimed at studying of the trends in the development of world monopolies and finding ways to reduce their concentration through public administration. The authors note that economic and legal approaches to the problem of monopoly and competition are not the same. Thus, the economic content of a monopoly is the power of the supplier of the product over the terms of its sale. The authors argue that when defining a monopoly situation, product markets are usually singled out, access to which is difficult for new competitors. To control market concentration, authorities calculate market concentration indices. Quantitative indicators are quite conditional, because there is not always a direct connection between the dimensional structure of the market and the behavior of enterprises - their prices, output and profitability.

Keywords: monopoly, public administration, concentration index, market.

Introduction

Monopoly in its various forms is an indispensable component of any economy. Its influence is growing along with the development of the economy. Objectively, this is facilitated by a constant increase in the number and types of goods and services, as well as the relative limited production resources for each product;

subjectively - the firm's "natural" desire for monopolization of the market in order to generate profits higher than the average level.

Consequences of monopoly economic activity can be negative (exclusive power) and positive (reduction of specific costs of production in case of increase of its volumes, concentration of capital, improvement of efficiency of investment and innovation policy, expansion and protection of markets, etc.).

But the negative consequences caused by the power of monopolies can be so devastating to the economy that almost every country has an antitrust regulator, the main purpose of which is precisely to neutralize them. Accordingly, the article is aimed at studying of the trends in the development of world monopolies and finding ways to reduce their concentration through public administration.

Literature review

The growth of monopolies in various industries negatively affected small and medium-sized companies. The article (Johan, Fransiska, 2023) examines the ways in which monopolistic practices such as anticompetitive behavior, predatory pricing, and barriers to entry systematically undermine competition and inhibit innovation. By studying the real-world examples and consequences faced by small businesses, this article sheds light on the urgent need to regulate monopoly activities to protect the viability of a market economy and create a level playing field for all businesses.

The authors of the work (Teachout, Zephyr, 2018) argue that when corporations exercise state power, either through monopolistic control over the market, or through participation in a campaign in support of state actors, they are subject to the same duties as those exercising state power. Therefore, in theory, we should call corporations corrupt when they selfishly exercise state power in such a way that their own interests are put above the interests of society. Because they make legal corporate corruption less likely, global anti-corruption campaigns should therefore step up antitrust drafting and campaign finance laws.

The authors of the article (Wei, Cui, An-Wei, Wan & Kumari, Sonia, 2022) believe that if the elasticity of substitution is less than 1, and capital and labor

complement each other, then the share of labor income tends to decrease. This is because the relative labor intensity tends to increase, while the growth rate of the capital-labor ratio tends to decrease. Empirical results also show that the decline in the share of labor income and wages is associated with monopoly and capital investment. If the volume of capital investments is higher and the degree of monopoly is higher, then labor income is lower and the share of labor income is lower. Monopolies and capital intercept much of the value created by the increased labor intensity, and workers make only small profits.

The monopoly now dominates the global oil market. The consequences of monopoly activities are often unexpected, and forecasting is more difficult than in a competitive environment. The authors of the article (M.A. Adelman, Soren Friis, 1974) illustrate the need to predict not only the impact of supply and demand, but also control over supply from a group of countries whose interests are not always the same, depending on political and economic factors.

Methodology

The empirical basis of the study is the concentration index (CR) is measured as the sum of the market shares of the largest firms operating in the market. The seller's market share can also be calculated on the basis of the ratio of the number of employees, the value of assets or the value added by a given firm to the total values for the market as a whole.

Main part

Economic and legal approaches to the problem of monopoly and competition are not the same. Thus, the economic content of a monopoly is the power of the supplier of the product over the terms of its sale. If this power is large, that is, there is a high concentration of the market on the supply side, then suppliers:

- limit production volumes;
- inflate prices;
- easily enter into conspiracies;
- block the access of new industry players [3; 9].

Therefore, the task of antimonopoly policy is to maintain an economically and socially acceptable level of market concentration so that competition disciplines enterprises and ensures appropriate resource utilization.

Market concentration is characterized by the structure of the product market and is determined by the specific weight of suppliers in the total volume of product supply. Changing the structure of product markets is not an easy task, because it requires taking into account the real and possible reaction of consumers to changes in the volume and price of the offer [7; 10].

The reaction of consumers depends on the characteristics of the product itself: quality, price elasticity of demand, etc. It is necessary to take into account the existence of alternatives that actually exist on the market, which can change the demand, as well as potential alternatives, the production capabilities of which are organized without major changes in technology. At the same time, the reaction of consumers to the state of the market depends on many conditions, the main of which is the saturation of demand [7; 10].

In addition, the geographical boundaries of the product market are not always easy to determine. The state of transport and communication has a significant impact on them. With unstable transport connections and high delivery costs, markets are easily divided into local ones, and vice versa, good communications greatly expand them. The geographic boundaries of markets also depend on how open the country's economy is to international trade.

The boundaries of commodity markets are too mobile for stable criteria to be possible for their determination. Therefore, antimonopoly laws do not contain such regulations. Market boundaries are determined by the executive or judicial authorities when considering conflict situations [5; 14].

When defining a monopoly situation, product markets are usually singled out, access to which is difficult for new competitors. In particular, among the barriers to access to new markets, the following stand out:

- savings on the scale of production and sales, which gives advantages in production costs;
- technological monopoly protected by patents;
- control over raw materials and overall vertical integration of enterprises;
- financial barrier - the need to invest large amounts of capital to access the market;
- sustainable consumer choice [9; 14].

To control market concentration, authorities calculate market concentration indices. Quantitative indicators are quite conditional, because there is not always a direct connection between the dimensional structure of the market and the behavior of enterprises - their prices, output and profitability.

However, many countries have laws that set market share thresholds which define a supplier's dominant position. These values are individual in each country. For example, in Germany, the position of one enterprise is considered dominant if its share exceeds 1/3 of the market, two enterprises - if it occupies more than 1/2, and three enterprises - if they occupy 2/3 of the market for a certain product. Japanese law defines a dominant position in a market where either the share of one largest supplier exceeds 50% or the share of the two largest suppliers exceeds 75% [5; 12].

The Japan Fair Trade Commission monitors the market for 485 product groups and annually publishes indices of production concentration of one, three and five largest manufacturers.

In Great Britain and France, the limits of the above indicators are the lowest: the manufacturer must not exceed 25% of the market share, and the amount of assets must also be determined.

In Japan, there is an additional regulator of firm size: a joint-stock company is prohibited from keeping its own shares on the balance sheet. It is clear that a company cannot buy its own shares and offer them for sale at a higher price in order to increase its equity capital.

The US Department of Justice establishes different approaches to the merger of enterprises – “horizontal”, “vertical” and “conglomerate” ones [8; 13].

The first type of merger (on the same product market) is regulated more strictly than the second (between contiguous partners) and the third ones. In particular, conglomerate mergers are mergers between enterprises of technologically unrelated industries. In addition to controlling the concentration along the lines of ownership relations, the laws of many countries prevent concentration at the management level, prohibiting the interweaving of the directorate, that is, the combination of management positions in competing companies.

Appropriate application of legislation on restrictive business practices allows to protect the national market from foreign monopolists in cases of damage to the national economy. The approach to monopolies from the standpoint of control and regulation makes it possible to determine the degree of possible and necessary influence on the monopolist every time. In particular, the ranking of the largest monopoly companies in the world is shown in Table 1 [4].

Table 1. The ranking of the largest monopoly companies in the world in 2023

Brand	Country	Brand cost in 2023, \$	Brand cost in 2022, \$
Amazon	USA	299 280	350 273
Apple	USA	297 512	355 080
Google	USA	281 382	263 425
Microsoft	USA	191 574	184 245
Walmart	USA	113 781	111 918
Samsung Group	South Korea	99 659	107 284
ICBC	China	69 545	75 119
Verizon	USA	67 443	69 639
Tesla	USA	66 207	46 010
TikTok/Douyin	China	65 696	58 980

Source: <https://inventure.com.ua/uk/tools/database/rejting-brendiv-2023:-najdorozhchi-brendi-svitu>

Nevertheless, despite the significant number of monopolies in the countries of the world, according to the forecast for GDP growth of the world's leading economies provided by the IMF, one can see an average increase of 3.0% in 2024.

In order to regulate concentration within the country in the context of export development, it may be useful to form large production units that have formal monopoly characteristics. Encouraging such concentration of production is one of the main points of the economic policy of most developed capitalist countries (EU, Japan). This is about concentration, which allows you to reduce production costs as much as possible and concentrate the development of product samples in one hand, increasing its competitiveness on the foreign market.

In order to determine the economic expediency of concentration in export industries, an analysis of the optimal dimensions of the production of relevant goods should be carried out not on a national scale, but on the scale of the world market. It is hardly expedient to destroy the created production if it meets the criteria of a monopoly in the domestic market, but has an optimal value from the point of view of export markets.

Liberalization of foreign economic activity, unification of standards, convergence of consumption style with foreign countries lead to the blurring of the border between products for export and for the domestic market.

Conclusions

Thus, in all countries, there are groups of industries excluded from the antitrust legislation. These are the so-called branches of direct state regulation or “natural monopolies”. Such industries include industries that meet the following criteria:

- are organized according to the principle of large-scale network economy with expensive equipment;
- are characterized by the amount of demand set by the technology (for example, the capacity of communication cables, the number of air frequencies, etc.);

- industries from the use of products of which an individual consumer cannot be excluded, that is, industries of the public sector: electric power, gas management, water supply, railway, air transport, communication, radio broadcasting, television.

Discussion

Antitrust law occupies a significant place in the economy and economic law as one of the ways of state regulation of the economy, namely, limiting the formation of monopolies, their use of monopoly power, as well as preventing illegal actions in competition.

For example, many countries of the world borrowed the main provisions of antitrust laws in the United States. However, each country has its own characteristics, which is reflected in their antitrust legislation. In particular, enforcement authorities vary significantly, the market share that a company must cover for it to become a monopoly.

Some lawyers and economists believe that it is time to move from the usual application of antitrust laws to closer estimates of the consequences of monopolization: low private investment in the industry, growing inequality in the market, lower business dynamics, etc.

References

1. M.A. Adelman, Soren Friis, Changing monopolies and European oil supplies: the shifting balance of economic and political power in the world oil market, *Energy Policy*, Volume 2, Issue 4, 1974, Pages 275-292.
2. Bain, J. S. (1941). The Profit Rate as a Measure of Monopoly Power. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 55(2), 271–293.
3. Blair, R. D., & Carruthers, C. K. (2010). The economics of monopoly power in antitrust. Chapter 4. In K. Hylton (Ed.), *Antitrust laws and economics* (p. 311). *Encyclopedia of law and economics*. Edward Elgar Publisher

4. Brand Rankings 2023: The World's Most Expensive Brands. URL: <https://inventure.com.ua/uk/tools/database/rejting-brendiv-2023:-najdorozhchi-brendi-svitu> (accessed: 01.02.2024).
5. Dealing with Monopolies and State Enterprises: WTO Rules for Goods and Services. URL: https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/reser_e/ti9801_e.htm (accessed: 01.02.2024).
6. International Monetary Fund. URL: <https://www.imf.org/en/Home> (accessed: 01.02.2023).
7. Johan, Fransiska, How Monopolies are Destroying Small and Medium-Sized Companies (July 13, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4508467> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4508467>.
8. Monopoly Examples. URL: <https://www.educba.com/monopoly-examples/> (accessed: 01.02.2024).
9. Sun, Z., Tang, D., and Li, Q. (2021). Competitive strategy of firms' participation in the global value chains and labor income share. *Complexity* 2021, 1–18. doi:10.1155/2021/8716737.
10. Teachout, Zephyr. “The Problem of Monopolies & Corporate Public Corruption.” *Daedalus* 147, no. 3 (2018): 111–26. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48563084>.
11. Young, A. T., and Tackett, M. Y. (2018). Globalization and the decline in labor shares: Exploring the relationship beyond trade and financial flows. *Eur. J. Political Econ.* 52, 18–35. doi:10.1016/j.ejpoleco.2017.04.003.
12. What are some examples of monopolies in the real world? URL: <https://www.quora.com/What-are-some-examples-of-monopolies-in-the-real-world> (accessed: 01.02.2024).
13. Why Monopolies Abroad Don't Justify Monopolies at Home. URL: <https://www.openmarketsinstitute.org/publications/monopolies-abroad-dont-justify-monopolies-home> (accessed: 01.02.2024).
14. Wei, Cui & An-Wei, Wan & Kumari, Sonia. (2022). Do more get more:

Monopoly appropriation of labor income in manufacturing companies. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*. 10. 10.3389/fenvs.2022.1037615.